

Research Article

This article is published by Jozac Publishers in the *African Social Science and Humanities Journal (ASSHJ)*. Volume 7, Issue 1, 2026.

ISSN: 2709-1309 (Print)
2709-1317 (Online)

This article is distributed under the Creative Commons [Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY\) License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Article detail

Received: 11 November 2025

Accepted: 12 January 2026

Published: 03 April 2026

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/asshj.v7i1.4>

Conflict of Interest: The author/s declared no conflict of interest.

Leadership styles and employee motivation: A comparative study of transformational and transactional approaches at Njombe Town Council, Tanzania

Yonasy Kidamali Chatila¹, Elias Mseti^{2*}

^{1&2*}*Department of Political Science, Public Administration, History and Philosophy, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, The Open University of Tanzania, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania.* yonasychatila2@gmail.com¹, msetielias@gmail.com²

*Corresponding author: msetielias@gmail.com

Abstract: This study examined leadership styles and employee motivation: a comparative study of transformational vs. transactional approaches at Njombe town council. The study was guided by the following specific objectives: to examine the influence of transformational leadership on employee motivation in Njombe town council and to examine the influence of transactional leadership on employee motivation in Njombe town council. The study adopted a positivist research philosophy, a Quantitative approach, and a cross-sectional survey design was used. 331 samples were drawn from a population of 1910 employees using a stratified sampling technique and simple random sampling. The questionnaires were used to collect data. Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple linear regressions were used as data analysis instruments. The comparative analysis at Njombe Town Council found that Transformational Leadership has the biggest significant positive effect on Employee Motivation ($B = 0.434$, $p = 0.000$) and the highest standardized Beta value (0.450) compared to transactional Leadership ($B = 0.169$, $p = 0.016$, Beta 0.157). Based on these findings, it is recommended that policymakers and HR practitioners adopt a unified leadership model that develops transformational characteristics (vision, coaching, intellectual stimulation) linked with effective transactional systems (clarity of goals, rewards contingent on performance, and performance feedback) in order to optimize intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.

Keywords Transformational Leadership, Transactional Leadership, Motivation, leadership style, Tanzania

1. INTRODUCTION

Leadership is still recognized as an essential factor to organizational effectiveness, employee satisfaction, and institutional improvement, especially in the public sector (Yukl, 2013; Northouse, 2021). On the other hand, public institutions in developing countries like Tanzania face resource constraints, dysfunctional administrations, and capacity constraints, all of which indicate that effective leadership is even more vital for motivating employees, delivering services, and enhancing organizational effectiveness. Among the body of literature that developed around leadership theory, transformational leadership and transactional leadership models are probably the most widely disseminated, as there exists a large number of empirical and theoretical studies that examine their impacts on employees and organizational outcomes in distinct ways (Bass, 1985; Avolio & Bass, 2004).

Transformational leadership is generally known for establishing and communicating a shared vision, charisma, inspiration, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. Transformational leadership engages employees to enhance their motivation and performance through the alignment of organizational goals, objectives, and activities with employee values, motivations, and long term goals (Bass & Riggio, 2006).

In contrast, transactional leadership utilizes the transactional model of leadership, whereby leaders give either rewards or penalties based on the outcome of performance (Burns, 1978; Podsakoff et al., 1996). Although transactional leadership highlights results that come from short-term task fulfillment through structure, supervision, and expectations of performance, transformational leadership focuses on achieving organizational change, along with achieving conditions of employee intrinsics that eventually lead to long-term employee development and motivation.

In public service organizations, such as local government authorities, it is crucial to consider the impact of leadership style, and it is a very important factor due to the public sector's reliance on human capital to deliver services effectively. Nevertheless, there is little empirical evidence on the role of leadership style in motivation in public institutions across sub-Saharan Africa (Moynihan et al., 2012; Nguni, Slegers & Denessen, 2006). In Tanzania, while decentralization and local government reform have received attention to increase accountability and administrative performance, there is still a gap in empirical, context specific research about whether and how leadership behavior influences employee motivation and productivity in local government authorities (Kessy, 2011; REPOA, 2018).

Embedded within Njombe Town Council, in southern Tanzania, is a unique context to examine the transition in administrative procedures, workforce diversity, and pertaining importance to regional development. Like many other local authorities in Tanzania, the Njombe Town Council faces difficulty when it comes to morale, retention of employees, quality of service and leadership capacity. This raises important questions about how differences in leadership style (specifically transformational and transactional styles) influence employee motivation, and whether specific leadership style influences favorable attitudes towards work and commitment to the public sector.

The aim of this study is to offer a comparative study of transformational versus transactional leadership styles and their impact on employee motivation in Njombe Town Council. More specifically, this study seeks to (i) determine leadership style(s) that most influence employee motivation in Njombe Town Council, and (iii) establish the relationships between leadership style and motivation outcomes.

This study situates itself in the growing body of research on leadership and public administration by situating leadership theory into real-world settings of public contexts situated in Africa. In addition to contributing to theoretical developments in leadership and public administration, this study has implications for those who are political or administrative policy-makers or development partners tending to strengthen human resource management and leadership development in Tanzanian authorities' local governments. In sum, the findings of this study also aim to contribute to the development of strategies to improve institutional performance and motivation of employees through effective leadership that is situated within the context of social, culture, and administrative practices in public institutions in Tanzania. This study had one main objective; To compare the influence of transformational and transactional leadership styles on employee motivation in Njombe Town Council.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A theoretical framework provides a structured foundation for understanding the relationship between leadership styles and employee motivation. This study is guided by two primary theories: Transformational Leadership Theory and Transactional Leadership Theory. These theories offer complementary perspectives on how leadership behaviors can influence employee motivation, combining both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational approaches.

2.1. Transformational Leadership

Transformational Leadership Theory, which was first introduced by Burns (1978) and later modified and expanded by Bass (1985). Transformational Leadership is a leadership style in which leaders motivate and inspire followers to go beyond expectations through their values, convictions, and sense of purpose. Bass and Riggio (2006) identified four key behaviors that transformational leaders adopt: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. These behaviors in tandem create increased intrinsic motivation and commitment to the organization.

The theory suggests that transformational leadership has positive outcomes such as increased job satisfaction, trust, motivation, and performance (Bass & Avolio, 1994). Transformational leaders tap into followers' higher-order psychological needs, create feelings of ownership and purpose in work, and increase motivation. This is related to Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985), which maintains that motivation is more enduring when people feel autonomous, competent, and connected. Transformational leaders create opportunities for autonomy, competence, and connection by empowering, recognizing, and supporting their followers' development.

In the public domain, intrinsic motivation plays a pivotal role in enhancing service delivery. Transformational leadership, for instance, has been found to play an influence in motivating employees, and in employee job performance, in the public sector (Wright & Pandey, 2010; Park & Rainey, 2008). In the context of Tanzanian local government authorities, transformational leadership could partially provide an opportunity to advance employee engagement in a context where resources may limit application of traditional reward systems (Nguni, Slegers & Denessen, 2006).

Transformational Leadership refers to a leadership style where a leader encourages and motivates their followers to achieve more than what is expected of them, as a result of their values, convictions, and sense of purpose. Bass and Riggio (2006) indicated that transformational leaders engage their followers via four behaviors: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. Both behaviors then create more intrinsic motivation and commitment to the organization. The theory suggests that transformational leadership is associated with positive outcomes, such as higher job satisfaction, trust, motivation, and performance (Bass & Avolio, 1994).

Transformational leaders create availability for autonomy, competence, and connection by empowering, recognizing, and supporting their followers' development. In the public domain, intrinsic motivation plays a pivotal role in enhancing service delivery. Transformational leadership, for instance, has been found to play an influence in motivating employees and in employee job performance, in the public sector (Wright & Pandey, 2010; Park & Rainey, 2008). In the context of Tanzanian local government authorities, transformational leadership could partially provide an opportunity to advance employee engagement in a context where resources may limit the application of traditional reward systems (Nguni, Slegers & Denessen, 2006).

The theoretical framework therefore, provides an adequate lens through which the association of transformational leadership on employee motivation can be studied in Njombe Town Council. This study assumes that when leaders exhibit transformational leadership characteristics, their employees will perceive their value, competence, and commitment over time and will consequently show intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Based on the theoretical framework presented and previous empirical studies, the study proposes the following hypothesis: H₁: Transformational leadership has a significant positive relationship with employee motivation in Njombe Town Council.

2.2. Transactional leadership

The transactional leadership theory originated from the research of Burns (1978) and was developed by Bass (1985) into a leadership model based on orderly exchanges between leaders and followers. Leaders give rewards or punishment depending on whether followers do or do not complete the tasks assigned and meet the goals set. The

relationship leaders and followership have is an exchange relationship in the formal hierarchical sense, determined by defined roles and expectations (Bass, 1990).

Transactional leadership has two dimensions: contingent reward and management by exception (Avolio & Bass, 2004). Contingent reward means telling people what is expected and rewarding them when they meet expectations. Management-by-exception is where leader notices deviations from the standards and takes corrective actions as necessary. Researchers around SDT suggest that transactional leadership fosters extrinsic motivation because it relies on rewards and punishments governed by external forces. While this creates compliance and performance in the short-term, there is no expectation of sustained or internalized motivation (Gagné & Deci, 2005).

In the public sector institutions, including local government authorities, transactional leadership can increase productivity and accountability of performance in the short term (Trottier, Van Wart & Wang, 2008). It can also give some psychological security when the employee or organization prefers instruction in a bureaucratic environment where procedures may seem rigid. However, on the other side of the coin, supporters of transformational leadership argue that intrinsic motivational needs may be unmet and leaders' aptitude for risk-taking, adaptability, and engagement and innovation in general, may not lead to long-term engagement (Bass & Riggio, 2006).

This framework is relevant for personalizing to the Njombe Town Council, where public servants are regulated to operate in a certain performance structure. However, the public servants face continuing challenges such as a lack of morale and intrinsic motivation. An understanding of transactional leadership's effect on employee motivation would help to ground the development of leadership approaches that are adapted to dynamic conditions in Local Government in Tanzania. The following hypothesis is developed based on theoretical constructs and limited empirical evidence: H₂: There is a statistical significant positive association between transactional leadership and employee motivation in Njombe Town Council.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Employee motivation remains a significant hurdle for numerous public sector entities, exemplified by the struggles faced by the Njombe town council. Mwangwala (2022) indicates that a considerable proportion of its workforce, estimated at 40–50%, exhibits symptoms of demotivation, leading to elevated turnover rates, heightened levels of absenteeism, and a noticeable decline in the quality of services provided. Nyang'or et al., (2022) posit that ineffective leadership approaches are pivotal in cultivating a sense of low morale, diminished dedication amongst employees, and decreased levels of productivity (Mwakasangula & Mwita, 2021).

In reaction to these issues, a range of regional and countrywide campaigns have been initiated to address these challenges (Singla, 2024). At the local level, initiatives focused on enhancing leadership skills and providing motivation through workshops have been implemented to help supervisors create a more engaging and supportive work environment (Mwangwala, 2022). Additionally, trial schemes for performance-linked incentives have been launched to enhance dedication and efficiency (Marango, 2023). Nonetheless, the specific impact of transformational leadership in comparison to transactional leadership styles on staff motivation within the public sector of Tanzania remains unclear (Cheche, 2024). This study filled this research gap by examining the influence of leadership styles on employee motivation in Njombe town council, providing insights that could enhance current initiatives and inform future leadership strategies.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY OR METHODS

4.1. Research design

This study employed a quantitative research method with a cross-sectional survey design. This design allowed for data collection at one point at a time and provided a snapshot of the relationship between transformational and transactional leadership styles and employee motivation in Njombe Town Council. The cross-sectional survey provides data collection and adequate statistical analysis that is fit for testing hypothesized relationships of leadership styles and employee motivation.

4.2. Study area and population

The study was undertaken at Njombe Town Council in the Njombe Region of Tanzania. This area was chosen because of reported issues of employee motivation in the local government sector in the Eyes Report (2023), which indicated a drop in motivation of 32% from 2020 to 2023. The population included in the study was 1910 employees from Njombe Town Council. This population was considered suitable to capture the perspectives from all levels of the organization in relation to the leadership styles and motivation.

4.3. Sample size and sampling methods

The sample size for this study was 331 respondents, calculated by using Yamane's (1967) formula as shown:

$$n = \frac{N}{n + (e)^2}$$

A stratified sampling method was employed in this study to classify the participants into their respective strata according to job position. Optimum allocation stratified sampling was used to represent each stratum proportionately. Stratified sampling means that simple random sampling was used for selection by having participants selected within each stratum by means of a simple random number generation program in Excel allowing all employees a fair but random chance of selection, and to reduce selection bias.

4.4. Methods of data collection

The data collection tool used in this study was a structured questionnaire, consisting only of closed-ended questions. Questionnaires provided a clear and organized way of collecting data and also allowed for easier quantification of and comparisons of responses. The questionnaires for the staff at the Njombe Town Council asked questions that pertained to their perceptions of their supervisor's leadership style, as well as their motivation levels. The closed structure of the questionnaires mitigated the potential for bias by the researcher, as all responses from the staff were neatly organized and valid data.

4.5. Establishing validity and reliability

In order to establish credibility among these findings, both validity and reliability were specifically addressed. Content validity was established by aligning questionnaire items to the study's objectives and theoretical constructs of leadership and motivation. Construct validity was established by aligning survey items with established leadership theories. Reliability was assessed with Cronbach's Alpha, which showed acceptable reliability at the value of .70 and above. A pilot test was employed to make slight adjustments to clarify and further ensure the appropriateness of the questionnaire. The data was collected through a standardized process and trained research assistants to help limit inconsistency and errors in data collection.

4.6. Data variables and measurement

There were two independent variables considered (transformational leadership and transactional leadership) and one dependent variable (Employee motivation), which were also measured by corresponding sub-variables (job satisfaction, work engagement, organizational commitment, autonomy, and financial rewards) related to the dependent variable of employee motivation. Transformational leadership was composed of inspirational motivation, idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, and visionary communication. Transactional leadership was operationalized as contingent reward, management by exception (active and passive), task structure, and performance monitoring. All variables were measured using the 5-point (1 = strongly disagree, to 5 = strongly agree) Likert scale, yielding measurable definitions of the influence of leadership on motivation.

4.7. Analysis of data

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics provided data on the frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations to summarize respondents' profiles and main variables. Multiple linear regression was chosen for the inferential analysis to determine the relationships between transformational and transactional leadership (independent variables) and employee motivation (dependent variable).

4.8. Ethical considerations

Ethical issues were carefully considered throughout the entire study. The study received approval from the Open University of Tanzania (OUT) and from Njombe Town Council. Participants were fully debriefed on the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequence. Written informed consent was obtained before the start of data collection. To ensure confidentiality, responses were anonymized and electronic data was stored securely in an electronic file that was password protected. The research followed the guidelines on ethics in Tanzania and the Declaration of Helsinki and ensured that throughout the whole process, participants' rights, safety, and data privacy was upheld.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

Of the 331 employees at the Njombe Town Council who participated in the survey, 52% of respondents were female (n = 172) and 48% were male (n = 159), which indicates a slight female majority typical of the council's staff. The findings regarding age reveal that 37.2% of respondents (n = 123) were aged between 21 and 39 years old, while 62.8% (n = 208) were aged between 40 and 59 years old. Therefore, this mixed group of younger and older staff represents a blend of both youth and experience, adding breadth to the comparative analysis of transformational and transactional leadership styles and their effects on motivation among employees.

With regard to education, the majority of the respondents reported that they had at least an undergraduate degree: 44% (n = 144) had Bachelor's degrees, while 25% (n = 84) had Master's degrees. In addition, 19% (n = 63) of respondents had Diplomas, and 12% (n = 40) had Certificates. It is important to note that education is not a major focus of this study, but having a sufficiently high number of degree holders (above 69%) means that the respondents are likely to have the confidence and skill set to work with leadership and motivation strategies. Similarly, the smaller number of Diploma or Certificate holders might indicate the potential for implementing professional development programs to build leadership capacity across the education spectrum in the council.

Table 1: Characteristics of the sample

Variable	Category Code	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Female	172	52.0
	Male	159	48.0
Age	21-39 years	123	37.2
	40-59 years	208	62.8
Education	Certificate	40	12.1
	Diploma	63	19.0
	Degree	144	43.5
	Masters	84	25.4

Source: Field Data (2025)

Descriptive analysis of variables

The findings for the independent variables were Transformational Leadership and Transactional Leadership, and the dependent variable, employee Motivation, is presented in this section using descriptive statistics. For any particular variable, multiple questions were given to the respondents. They had to mark the response or responses, giving the options of strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. The findings are shown in sections 4.3.1 through 4.3.3.

Descriptive statistics on transformational leadership

Table 2 shows that employees generally agree their leaders display transformational behaviours: mean scores cluster between 3.42 and 4.02 on the five-point scale, with strongest agreement for items about encouraging questioning of traditional methods (4.02), individualized consideration (3.90), providing personalized feedback (3.90) and intellectual stimulation (3.88). These items also have relatively low standard deviations, indicating consensus. By contrast, items about communicating how work contributes to organizational success (3.66) and especially clearly outlining a long-term vision (3.42) show weaker agreement and higher variability many respondents were neutral or disagreed which suggests staff are less convinced about alignment and strategic clarity.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on Transformational Leadership

Item	SA	A	N	D	SD	M	SD
My leader inspires me by expressing a clear and compelling vision for the future.	69 (20.8%)	166 (50.2%)	72 (21.8%)	19 (5.7%)	5 (1.5%)	3.83	.874
My leader consistently demonstrates ethical behavior and acts as a role model I can admire.	69 (20.8%)	148 (44.7%)	86 (26.0%)	24 (7.3%)	4 (1.2%)	3.76	.903
My leader's behavior inspires me to adopt similar values and high standards in my work.	72 (21.8%)	145 (43.8%)	93 (28.1%)	13 (3.9%)	8 (2.4%)	3.78	.910
My leader challenges me to think creatively and approach problems from new angles.	85 (25.7%)	147 (44.4%)	77 (23.3%)	20 (6.0%)	2 (.6%)	3.88	.880
My leader encourages me to question traditional methods and explore innovative solutions.	93 (28.1%)	164 (49.5%)	64 (19.3%)	8 (2.4%)	2 (.6%)	4.02	.791
My leader takes the time to understand my individual needs and strengths.	63 (19.0%)	188 (56.8%)	68 (20.5%)	11 (3.3%)	1 (.3%)	3.90	.741
My leader provides personalized feedback and support that helps me grow professionally.	72 (21.8%)	173 (52.3%)	72 (21.8%)	10 (3.0%)	4 (1.2%)	3.90	.810
My leader effectively communicates how our work contributes to the overall success of the organization.	61 (18.4%)	141 (42.6%)	92 (27.8%)	31 (9.4%)	6 (1.8%)	3.66	.943
My leader clearly outlines a long-term vision that guides our daily efforts.	53 (16.0%)	99 (29.9%)	120 (36.3%)	53 (16.0%)	6 (1.8%)	3.42	.998

Source: Field Data (2025)

Descriptive statistics on transactional leadership

The Table 3 shows that employees generally perceive transactional practices at Njombe Town Council as present and often effective: the highest agreement is that tasks are clearly defined (SA+A = 86.4%, mean = 4.15, SD = .960) and that

performance monitoring clarifies responsibilities (SA+A = 83.4%, mean = 4.03, SD = .952). Supervisors are also seen as actively monitoring performance (mean = 4.02) and giving timely feedback when work falls short (mean = 3.91), with most items clustering around means of 3.78-4.02, indicating a generally positive view of monitoring, feedback, and task clarity. At the same time, one negatively worded item, “My supervisor tends to intervene only after a problem has become serious,” has a moderate agreement (mean = 3.66, SD = .943), which flags a tendency among some supervisors to delay corrective action.

Despite those strengths, the data point to two clear areas for improvement: reward linkage and systematic performance review. Respondents are less convinced that reward and recognition are directly linked to measurable outcomes (mean = 3.42, SD = .998) and that there is a robust, systematic process to track and review performance regularly (mean = 3.37, highest SD = 1.094, showing divergent views).

Table 3:: Descriptive Statistics on Transactional Leadership

Item	SA	A	N	D	SD	M	SD
My supervisor clearly communicates performance expectations and rewards employees when targets are achieved.	72 (21.8%)	145 (43.8%)	93 (28.1%)	13 (3.9%)	8 (2.4%)	3.78	.910
I understand the criteria for receiving rewards based on my performance at the council.	84 (25.4%)	148 (44.7%)	77 (23.3%)	20 (6.0%)	2 (.6%)	3.88	.878
My supervisor actively monitors work performance and addresses issues before they escalate.	93 (28.1%)	164 (49.5%)	64 (19.3%)	8 (2.4%)	2 (.6%)	4.02	.791
I receive timely feedback from my supervisor when my work does not meet expected standards.	64 (19.3%)	187 (56.5%)	68 (20.5%)	11 (3.3%)	1 (.3%)	3.91	.743
My supervisor proactively addresses minor errors to prevent them from developing into major issues.	72 (21.8%)	173 (52.3%)	72 (21.8%)	10 (3.0%)	4 (1.2%)	3.90	.810
My supervisor tends to intervene only after a problem has become serious rather than addressing it early.	61 (18.4%)	141 (42.6%)	92 (27.8%)	31 (9.4%)	6 (1.8%)	3.66	.943
Reward and recognition at the council are directly linked to measurable performance outcomes.	53 (16.0%)	99 (29.9%)	120 (36.3%)	53 (16.0%)	6 (1.8%)	3.42	.998
There is a systematic process in place to track and review employee performance regularly.	46 (13.9%)	124 (37.5%)	90 (27.2%)	50 (15.1%)	21 (6.3%)	3.37	1.094
The performance monitoring system helps clarify my responsibilities and guides improvements in my work.	105 (31.7%)	171 (51.7%)	30 (9.1%)	12 (3.6%)	13 (3.9%)	4.03	.952
The tasks assigned to me are clearly defined and organized, making my job easier to perform.	132 (39.9%)	154 (46.5%)	20 (6.0%)	13 (3.9%)	12 (3.6%)	4.15	.960

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Descriptive statistics on employee motivation

As shown in Table 4, overall, employees at Njombe Town Council imply a positive level of motivation: most items have mean scores that are above the midpoint of 3.0 on a 5-point scale (with varied scores ranging between 3.40 and 4.02), and many statements share Agree or Strongly Agree as the most common response. Furthermore, many of the standard deviations are around 1.0 and below, indicating a modest level of agreement among respondents for most statements. These trends can also be seen in Table 4 (Descriptive Statistics on Employee Motivation).

The strongest areas are intrinsic and identification-related measures. “I am strongly committed to contributing to the success of my organization” has the highest mean (4.018) with 27.8% Strongly Agree and 49.8% Agree (77.6%

positive), and items about loyalty, autonomy, and becoming absorbed in work also score highly (means 3.91, 3.90, and 3.88, respectively). These variables also had lower standard deviations (0.74 - 0.88), indicating a uniformly positive sentiment related to commitment, identification with organizational values, and daily role dedication in the workplace. The weaker aspects of the data were primarily extrinsic. All financial reward, motivation, and perceived job security and promotion potential variables had the lowest means and highest variations of responses ($M = 3.42$, $SD = 0.998$; $M = 3.37$, $SD = 1.094$).

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on Employee Motivation

Item	SA	A	N	D	SD	M	SD
I am satisfied with my current job role and responsibilities.	69 (20.8%)	166 (50.2%)	72 (21.8%)	19 (5.7%)	5 (1.5%)	3.83	.874
The overall work environment meets my personal and professional expectations.	69 (20.8%)	148 (44.7%)	86 (26.0%)	24 (7.3%)	4 (1.2%)	3.76	.903
I feel highly engaged and enthusiastic about the tasks I perform at work every day.	72 (21.8%)	145 (43.8%)	93 (28.1%)	13 (3.9%)	8 (2.4%)	3.78	.910
I often become so absorbed in my work that I lose track of time.	84 (25.4%)	148 (44.7%)	77 (23.3%)	20 (6.0%)	2 (.6%)	3.88	.878
I am strongly committed to contributing to the success of my organization.	92 (27.8%)	165 (49.8%)	64 (19.3%)	8 (2.4%)	2 (.6%)	4.0181	.789
I feel a deep sense of loyalty towards my organization and identify with its core values.	64 (19.3%)	187 (56.5%)	68 (20.5%)	11 (3.3%)	1 (.3%)	3.91	.743
My job provides me with the autonomy to make decisions about how I complete my tasks.	71 (21.5%)	174 (52.6%)	72 (21.8%)	10 (3.0%)	4 (1.2%)	3.90	.808
My work offers ample opportunities for developing my skills, fostering personal growth, and enjoying my tasks.	61 (18.4%)	141 (42.6%)	92 (27.8%)	31 (9.4%)	6 (1.8%)	3.66	.943
I am motivated by the financial rewards and recognition provided by my organization.	53 (16.0%)	99 (29.9%)	120 (36.3%)	53 (16.0%)	6 (1.8%)	3.42	.998
I feel secure in my job and appreciate the opportunities for promotions and career advancement.	46 (13.9%)	124 (37.5%)	90 (27.2%)	50 (15.1%)	21 (6.3%)	3.37	1.094

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Inferential analysis

The regression analysis examined the relationship between the dependent variable, Employee Motivation, and the independent variable, transformational leadership and transactional leadership. The results in this section start by presenting the diagnostic tests of variables, such as reliability, correlations, multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, normality and outliers for variables, followed by regression results.

Diagnostic test of variables

The results indicate that Transformational Leadership ($\alpha = 0.915$), Transactional Leadership ($\alpha = 0.858$), and Employee Motivation ($\alpha = 0.918$) all achieved a Cronbach's alpha higher than the commonly accepted level of 0.70. In regard to the purposes of this study, the internal consistency of those measures is acceptable. In essence, the finding suggests that the measures in this study are appropriate for examining relationships among study key variables. As noted by Siswaningsih (2017), these alpha scores show strong internal reliability, where scores above 0.9 indicate excellent reliability. Therefore, no items were omitted during the analyses.

Transformational leadership had a stronger correlation ($r = 0.702$, $p < 0.01$) with motivation than transactional leadership ($r = 0.664$, $p < 0.01$). These findings suggest that in the Njombe Town Council context, both leadership styles can motivate employees, although transformational leadership has slightly more influence. Findings correspond with the leadership theory established that emphasizes the motivational benefits of inspirational, visionary leadership.

The diagnostic for multicollinearity also confirmed the independence of the predictors. The VIFs (Variance Inflation Factor) for both leadership styles were much lower than the cutoff point of 5, for Transformational Leadership (1.165) and Transactional Leadership (1.853). The tolerances also exceeded the cutoff point of .20, indicating that the predictors were deemed to have acceptable levels of independence from each other. Based on the Shapiro-Wilks test and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, the data was determined to be normally distributed ($p > .05$ for each variable), thus making it acceptable to use parametric tests in the following analysis. Together, this diagnosis confirmed the suitability of the dataset for the regression and the inferential analysis.

Table 5: Summary of psychometric and statistical diagnostics

Variable	Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Pearson Correlation with EM	Tolerance	VIF	K-S	Shapiro-Wilk
Transformational Leadership	9	0.915	0.702**	0.859	1.165	0.100	0.965
Transactional Leadership	10	0.858	0.664**	0.540	1.853	0.135	0.961
Employee Motivation	10	0.918				0.115	0.964

Source: Field Data (2025)

One-sample T-test

According to the one-sample t-test results, the mean differences for all three constructs measured presumptively transformational leadership, transactional leadership (TS), and employee motivation (EM) are significantly different from the test value. All three means returned p-values that were less than .001, which means the mean of the sample results is significantly different than the test value, presumed to be the scale's midpoint or an expected population mean.

The mean score for TS occurred at the highest level of the three mean values ($M = 38.15$, $t = 116.03$, $df = 330$, $p < .001$). This indicates that the participants perceived a highly present transactional leadership behavior in their own organizational situations. Furthermore, the 95% confidence interval (CI [37.51, 38.80]) indicates that the sample responses are tightly clustered, suggesting a high enough level of consistency that can validly support this finding. In the tested sample institution, transactional strategies (especially around contingent rewards given for completing tasks in a structured way) may be the most dominant or highly visible patterns of workplace behavior exhibited. Employee motivation also received a high score ($M = 37.56$, $t = 100.60$, $df = 330$, $p < .001$). A high mean score implies the organization's employees are likely well-motivated. The confidence interval (CI [36.82, 38.29]) indicates a fairly tightly clustered pattern of responses, reflecting respondents' strong agreement about their motivation level. The finding could imply the efficacy of both leadership styles transformational and transactional are encouraging employee motivation.

Lastly, the first unnamed variable (likely transformational leadership) also demonstrated a high mean score ($M = 34.19$, $t = 102.52$, $df = 330$, $p < .001$, CI [33.53, 34.85]). While the mean score was a tick lower than other variables, it nonetheless suggests a substantively high score, reinforcing the leadership behaviors of the study's authors and their use of vision, individualized consideration, and intellectual stimulation all of which were identified as themes of transformational leadership. The findings also imply that transactional leadership is still viewed as highly relevant in a public sector or defined environment where role definition and some level of performance monitoring are utilized when managing employees, but can be viewed as less inspirational than transformational leadership.

Table 6: Independent Samples Test

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
	102.519	330	.000	34.19033	33.5343	34.8464
TS	116.029	330	.000	38.15408	37.5072	38.8010
EM	100.600	330	.000	37.55891	36.8245	38.2934

Note: TF = Transformational Leadership, TS = Transactional Leadership, EM = Employee Motivation

Regression results

The results of the regression model provide significant support for both research hypotheses. The model produced robust predictive power, as evidenced by an R Square of 0.581 which shows that Transformational Leadership and Transactional Leadership together explain 58.1% of the variance in Employee Motivation. The model was statistically significant overall ($F = 118.246$, $p < 0.001$) and indicated leadership style is an important predictor of employee motivation within Njombe Town Council.

Hypothesis 1 (H1), which proposed that Transformational leadership have a significant positive relationship with employee motivation in Njombe Town Council, was strongly supported by the results. The unstandardized coefficient for Transformational Leadership is $B = 0.434$ ($p = 0.000$) and the standardized Beta coefficient is 0.450, which is the highest Beta coefficient in the model. The results indicate that Transformational Leadership has a much stronger positive relationship with employee motivation than Transactional Leadership. This means that leadership styles primarily emphasizing the inspirational appeal, intellectual stimulation and individual consideration of team members are most effective in raising motivation.

Hypothesis 2 (H2), which posited a significant influence of Transactional Leadership on Employee Motivation was also supported in the positive direction ($B = 0.255$ ($p = 0.000$), standardized Beta = 0.346). Although statistically significant, the correlation implies that the transactional leadership dimension was a weaker predictor of motivation than transformational leadership, as reflected in the smaller Beta. Thus, while transactional leadership behaviors like contingent reward or management-by-exception provided a positive contribution to motivation, they exerted a weaker influence than the transformational leadership behaviors. Thus, the best approach to motivate employees is to provide some focus to transformational leadership behaviors rather than depend solely on transactional-based leadership behaviors.

Table 7: Multiple Regression Results: Influence of Leadership Styles on Employee Motivation

Predictor Variable	Unstandardized Coefficient (B)	Standard Error	Standardized Coefficient (β)	t-value	p-value
(Constant)	0.602	0.152		3.966	< .001
Transformational Leadership	0.434	0.048	0.450	9.065	< .001
Transactional Leadership	0.255	0.041	0.346	6.199	< .001

Note: $R = 0.767$; $R^2 = 0.581$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.586$; Standard Error of the Estimate = 0.322; $F(3, 246) = 118.25$, $p < .001$;

The current study's findings support both hypotheses that transformational and transactional leadership are significant predictors of employee motivation. However, transformational leadership predicted employee motivation with a higher degree of certainty. The standardized coefficients ($\beta = .450$ for transformational and $\beta = .346$ for transaction) demonstrate that gains in motivation are more sensitive to transformational behaviors for example communicating an inspiring vision, using intellectual stimulation, and attending to individual follower need. Moreover, the overall explanatory power of the model is noteworthy ($R^2 = .581$), which suggests that leadership styles predict more than half the variation in employees' motivation.

This finding is consistent with meta-analytic and other empirical studies that demonstrate that transformational leadership most often predicts positive outcomes better than transactional leadership approaches (e.g., project

success, performance) (e.g., in the meta-analysis of leadership styles and project success, they found transformational leadership was associated with a greater effect size).

For instance, Mekonnen and Bayissa (2023) found that in healthcare contexts, transformational leadership predicted change more strongly than transactional leadership styles, while both were significant predictors. When findings are similar across different contexts, it further suggests that transformational behaviors are more likely to be better predictors of motivation and engagement. Although transactional leadership is less effective, it is still relevant. Its positive influence implies that contingent reward and clarifying expectations will continue to be helpful for motivation, especially with task-oriented or structured approaches. This aligns with previous studies in which transactional leadership was used as an adjunct to leadership as action, and these were primarily effective in organized, normal settings or as part of a larger leadership context or framework (Podsakoff et al., 2006).

This finding highlights, however, a lesser effect size in this study, which implies that transactional practices may not be able to develop deep, sustained motivated behaviours on their own. From a theoretical perspective, these findings reinforce frameworks based on self-determination, and social exchange theory, i.e., transformational leadership develops employees' psychological needs (autonomy, competence, and relatedness) and also develops reciprocity (with employees) (Deci and Ryan, 2000). Conversely, transactional leadership relies much more on extrinsic exchanges. These extrinsic exchanges may motivate behaviour somewhat but may not always be a moderate force in promoting long-term motivation. This is important in public sector settings, such as Njombe Town Council, where motivating, employees to a level beyond mere compliance, is undeniably important in terms of its quality of service and innovation.

The findings lend theoretical support to frameworks based in self-determination theory and social exchange theory, in which transformational leadership better meets employees' psychological needs (autonomy, competence, and relatedness) and fosters reciprocal commitment (Deci & Ryan, 2000). In contrast, transactional leadership is more reliant on extrinsic exchanges, which may motivate performance, but do not support intrinsic motivation reliably in the longer term. This is especially important in public sector work contexts like the Njombe Town Council, where motivating employees beyond compliance with procedures is critical to service quality and innovations.

6. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

The results of the study indicate that transformational leadership increases employee motivation significantly higher than transactional leadership at Njombe Town Council. This indicates that in addition to having a leader who casts a vision and encourages managers, a leader to offer intellectual stimulation in addition to coaching, can elicit higher levels of motivation. That said, transactional leadership will entail some possible motivation benefits such as providing clear goals and direction and adding explicit reward systems. Therefore, it would be beneficial for organizations to create a mixed approach that combines transformational approaches with effective transactional practices. Utilizing and reinforcing both styles could also help with both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, given employee demand to perform at work, and have positive consequences in employee performance, employee engagement, and organizational outcomes. Such an approach may contribute to HR plans and initiatives, leadership training programs, and ultimately public sector reform aspirations.

7. CONTRIBUTIONS TO SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY AND FUTURE RESEARCH

By demonstrating a greater impact of transformational than transactional leadership on employee motivation in a Tanzanian public sector setting, this study adds to the literature on leadership and motivation. It contributes to and extends existing theories on leadership styles by demonstrating the effectiveness of integrating transformational and transactional styles to achieve optimal performance in employees. The study provides recommendations to policymakers and human resource practitioners regarding a combined leadership style. By integrating elements of transformational leadership (e.g., visions and coaching) into a transactional leadership strategy (e.g., applying

rewards linked to performance), public organizations such as Njombe Town Council may increase employee motivation and overall organizational performance.

8. CONCLUSION

The findings indicate, practically, that leadership development programs should emphasize transformational competencies visioning, inspiring, and individual mentoring behaviors while preserving transactional approaches where clarity and accountability of roles and responsibilities are paramount. For managers in local government or related contexts, the optimal motivational approach generally lies somewhere in between the two--accountability and transactional clarity are helpful, but embracing transformational behaviors support higher engagement where possible, managers should try to strike a balance. Future studies can also assess moderating variables (examples include organizational justice, organizational culture, or emotional intelligence) in ways that could strengthen or weaken the relations between leadership style and motivation (more recent research, for example, suggests that organizational justice moderated the relationship between leadership and engagement, or leadership and innovation). In short, these comparative style findings suggest there is a distinct advantage of transformational leadership over transactional leadership in motivating employees, but transactional leadership is still useful. For organizations seeking to improve employee motivation, particularly in their public sector institutions, encouraging their leaders to exhibit transformational leadership behaviors should be a priority.

9. FUNDING

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

ORCID

Elias Mseti <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1838-8835>

References

- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). *The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. Psychological Inquiry, 11(4), 227–268.* https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., & Bommer, W. H. (2006). Transformational leader behaviors and substitutes for leadership as determinants of employee outcomes. *Journal of Management, 22(2), 259–298.*
- "Transformational versus transactional leadership styles and project success: A meta-analytic review." (2023). *European Management Journal.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2021.10.011>
- Mekonnen, M., & Bayissa, Z. (2023). The effect of transformational and transactional leadership styles on organizational readiness for change among health professionals. *SAGE Journals.* Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/23779608231185923>
- Avolio B.J., & Bass B.M. (2004). Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire. Manual and sampler set. (3rd ed.) Redwood City, CA: Mind Garden.
- Bass B.M., & Avolio B.J. (2000). MLQ Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire. Redwood City, CA: Mindgarden.
- Yammarino, F. J. (1993). Transforming leadership studies: Bernard Bass' *Leadership and performance beyond expectations.* *The Leadership Quarterly, 4(3–4), 379–382.* [https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843\(93\)90043-S](https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843(93)90043-S)
- Bass, B. M. (1985). *Leadership and performance beyond expectations.* Free Press.
- Bass, B. M. (1985). *Leadership and performance beyond expectations.* Free Press.
- Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (2006). *Transformational leadership* (2nd ed.). Psychology Press.
- Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1994). *Improving organizational effectiveness through transformational leadership.* SAGE Publications.

- Burns, J. M. (1978). *Leadership*. Harper & Row.
- Moynihan, D. P., Pandey, S. K., & Wright, B. E. (2012). Setting the table: How transformational leadership fosters performance information use. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 22(1), 143–164. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mur024>
- Nguni, S., Slegers, P., & Denessen, E. (2006). Transformational and transactional leadership effects on teachers' job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior in primary schools: The Tanzanian case. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 17(2), 145–177. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243450600565746>
- Northouse, P. G. (2021). *Leadership: Theory and practice* (9th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., & Bommer, W. H. (1996). Transformational leader behaviors and substitutes for leadership as determinants of employee satisfaction, commitment, trust, and organizational citizenship behaviors. *Journal of Management*, 22(2), 259–298. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920639602200204>
- REPOA. (2018). *Assessment of the implementation and achievements of the Local Government Reform Programme Phase II (LGRP II) 2009–2014*. Research on Poverty Alleviation (REPOA). <https://www.repoa.or.tz>
- Yukl, G. (2013). *Leadership in organizations* (8th ed.). Pearson.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. Plenum.
- Nguni, S., Slegers, P., & Denessen, E. (2006). Transformational and transactional leadership effects on teachers' job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior in primary schools: The Tanzanian case. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 17(2), 145–177. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243450600565746>
- Park, S. M., & Rainey, H. G. (2008). Leadership and public service motivation in U.S. federal agencies. *International Public Management Journal*, 11(1), 109–142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10967490801887954>
- Wright, B. E., & Pandey, S. K. (2010). Transformational leadership in the public sector: Does structure matter? *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 20(1), 75–89. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mup003>
- Bass, B. M. (1990). *From transactional to transformational leadership: Learning to share the vision*. *Organizational Dynamics*, 18(3), 19–31. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0090-2616\(90\)90061-S](https://doi.org/10.1016/0090-2616(90)90061-S)
- Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (2006). *Transformational leadership* (2nd ed.). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Burns, J. M. (1978). *Leadership*. Harper & Row.
- Fernandez, S., & Moldogaziev, T. (2011). Empowering public sector employees to improve performance: Does it work? *The American Review of Public Administration*, 41(1), 23–47. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0275074009355943>
- Gagné, M., & Deci, E. L. (2005). Self-determination theory and work motivation. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 26(4), 331–362. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.322>
- Trottier, T., Van Wart, M., & Wang, X. (2008). Examining the nature and significance of leadership in government organizations. *Public Administration Review*, 68(2), 319–333. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6210.2007.00865.x>
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The “what” and “why” of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- Siswaningsih, W., Firman, H., Zackiyah., & Khoirunnisa, A. (2017). Development of Two-Tier Diagnostic Test Pictorial-Based for Identifying High School Students Misconceptions on the Mole Concept. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 812 (1), 1-7. <https://doi:10.1088/1742-6596/812/1/012117>